

ASSESSMENT OF ACCEPTABILITY AND SHELF LIFE OF COOKIES ENRICHED WITH GROUND, CANDIED, AND DEHYDRATED BAMBOO SHOOTS

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted primarily to formulate cookies enriched with bamboo shoots and assess their acceptability among panelists. Evaluation criteria are color, aroma, texture, flavor, and overall acceptability of cookies enriched with ground, candied, and dehydrated bamboo shoots. Furthermore, the study investigated the shelf life of these cookies. The cookie treatments were analyzed through sensory evaluation involving 51 panelists. Results indicated that cookies containing candied bamboo shoots were most preferred in terms of color, flavor, and overall acceptability, while the control sample exhibited superior aroma. The treatment comprising cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots, was favored for its texture. Moreover, cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots demonstrated the longest shelf life compared to other treatments.

Keywords: *Bamboo Shoots, Cookies, Product Development, Sensory Evaluation, Product Acceptability, Shelf Life*

INTRODUCTION

To ensure the health and nutrition of students participating in the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP), it is imperative to offer snacks that adhere to the guidelines stipulated in Department Order No. 34, Series of 2017, emphasizing the significance of providing wholesome foods. This directive is in line with the principles outlined in Department Order No. 13, Series of 2017, which advocates for healthy dietary choices within educational institutions and DepEd offices.

While commercial cookies may be convenient, they often pose health disadvantages due to their high sugar, fat, and calorie content (Johnson et al., 2016).

Additionally, unhealthy cookies typically lack essential nutrients and may contribute to adverse health effects such as weight gain, elevated blood sugar levels, and increased risk of chronic diseases like diabetes and cardiovascular conditions (Brown et al., 2019). Furthermore, the consumption of commercial and unhealthy cookies can lead to a range of health issues beyond those associated with excessive sugar and fat intake.

These cookies often contain refined flours and artificial additives, which offer little nutritional value and may even contribute to inflammation and impaired immune function (de Punder & Pruimboom, 2015). The high glycemic index of such cookies can also result in rapid spikes and subsequent crashes in blood sugar levels, leading to feelings of fatigue and hunger shortly after consumption (Ludwig, 2019). Moreover, the overconsumption of processed snacks like these has been linked to an increased risk of obesity and metabolic syndrome, further underscoring the importance of offering healthier alternatives within the SBFP (Malik et al., 2013). By incorporating bamboo shoots into snacks, not only can these detrimental health effects be mitigated, but students can also benefit from the nutritional value and versatility of this locally available ingredient.

Abundant in Mankayan, Benguet, bamboo shoots are versatile ingredients that are underexplored in baking despite their culinary diversity, ranging from stir-fries to salads (Sohail et al., 2023). Research highlights the nutritional benefits of bamboo shoots, including high dietary fiber content, low calorie and fat content, and a wealth of vitamins (C, A, B6), minerals (potassium, magnesium), and antioxidants (Xu et al., 2018). The significant fiber content in bamboo shoots promotes gastrointestinal health by supporting regular bowel movements and fostering a favorable gut microbiome environment, potentially alleviating digestive issues such as constipation and hemorrhoids (Chen et al., 2012).

Given these considerations, the researcher would like to explore the acceptability of cookies enriched with bamboo shoots as a viable snack option for the School-Based Feeding Program. This innovative approach not only aligns with the SBFP's objective of offering nutritious snacks but also harnesses local resources to enhance the overall health and well-being of students.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to develop cookies enriched with bamboo shoots using creaming method. Specifically, it aims to:

1. determine the consumer's acceptability of cookies enriched with ground, candied, and dehydrated bamboo shoots in terms of color, aroma, texture, flavor and overall acceptability; and
2. determine the shelf life of cookies enriched with ground, candied, and dehydrated bamboo shoots.

METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the locale of the study, research design, respondents, research instruments, materials, and methods used in conducting the study.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Lepanto National High School, Paco, Mankayan, Benguet. Various formulations were prepared at the researcher's residence, and sensory evaluations were conducted with some learners of the said school.

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research design. Sensory Evaluation Questionnaire was used to determine acceptability of the cookie treatments.

Research Respondents

The panelists were composed of 51 individuals of both sexes from Lepanto National High School. These group of panelists are considered as consumer-type panelists.

Research Instrument

To determine the level of acceptability of the panelists in terms of color, aroma, texture, flavor, and overall acceptability of the samples, nine-point hedonic scale was used.

Materials

The bamboo shoots used were gathered within Paco, Mankayan. The utensils and/or equipment used are oven, mixing bowl, electric mixer, rubber scraper, measuring cups, measuring spoons, cookie cutter, baking pan, weighing scale, kitchen knife, dehydrator, food processor, non-stick pan, and wooden spoon. The ingredients needed in preparing the cookies are all-purpose flour, white sugar, brown sugar, unsalted butter, egg, vanilla extract, baking soda, salt, and bamboo shoots.

In conducting the sensory evaluation, plates, plastic spoons, and cookie samples were used. Appropriate scorecards were also provided for the panelists to record their judgements on the given samples. Further, bottles of water were available for the panelists to cleanse their palate before and after tasting each sample.

Table 1 presents the ingredients in making the control sample and treatments of cookies enriched with bamboo shoots. It also indicates the measurements needed for every sample.

Table 1. Measurement of ingredients in preparing cookies enriched with bamboo shoots

INGREDIENTS	TREATMENTS			
	327	273	732	372
	Control	Ground	Candied	Dehydrated
All-purpose flour	313 g	313 g	313 g	313 g
butter	125 g	125 g	125 g	125 g
white sugar	63 g	63 g	63 g	63 g
brown sugar	125 g	125 g	125 g	125 g
egg	57 g	57 g	57 g	57 g
vanilla extract	6 g	6 g	6 g	6 g
baking soda	3 g	3 g	3 g	3 g
salt	3 g	3 g	3 g	3 g
bamboo shoots (ground)	-	225g	-	-
bamboo shoots (candied)	-	-	225g	-
bamboo shoots (dehydrated)	-	-	-	225g

Methods

This section discusses the method used in preparing the control sample and the different treatments of cookies enriched with bamboo shoots.

A. Preparation of Bamboo Shoots

The bamboo shoots as enrichment were prepared by peeling the outside leafy covering, washing, cutting into strips, boiling, and processing. The procedures applied in processing the bamboo shoots are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Procedures of preparing different pre-treatments of bamboo shoots

Bamboo Shoots (Ground)	Bamboo Shoots (Candied)	Bamboo Shoots (Dehydrated)
1. Grind bamboo shoots using a food processor (SUS 304).	1. Boil 1/2 cup water using non-stick pan. Add 3 cups of brown sugar, dissolve and let it caramelize.	1. Arrange the bamboo shoot strips on the dehydrator trays (Nontaus Fruit Dehydrator, JZE-R2 (A)), and dehydrate it at 700 C for 5 hours.
	2. Add 1kg bamboo shoot strips. Stir and let the water evaporate until crystalized sugar will coat the bamboo shoot strips.	

B. Preparation of Cookies Enriched with Bamboo Shoots

The creaming method was adopted for the control and all treatments of the cookies. The first procedure is to preheat the oven at 350°F (La Germania, SL155 40WT was used). Cover baking sheet (13"x 16") with parchment paper. Measure all ingredients using a digital weighing scale (Electronic Kitchen Scale, SF-400). In a mixing bowl (9" Ø, 6"h), combine all-purpose flour (313g), salt (3g), and baking soda (3g). Mix well and set aside. In a separate bowl, put the butter (125g) then cream it using electric mixer (Imarflex, IMX-270B, SN: 4456 used). Gradually add sugar and continue beating until texture becomes fluffy. Add vanilla extract (6g) and egg (57g) then continue mixing for 2 minutes. Gradually add all-purpose flour, salt, and baking soda mixture and beat until all the ingredients are well-mixed. Add bamboo shoots, fold until bamboo shoots are well incorporated.

The bamboo shoot enrichment varies, no bamboo shoot was added for the control sample; and 225g ground bamboo shoots, 225g candied bamboo shoots, and 225g dehydrated bamboo shoots for treatments 273, 732, and 372 respectively. Scoop and drop the mixture on the baking sheet covered with parchment paper. Bake for 10-12 minutes. After baking, the cookies will be cooled and packed in polypropylene plain low-density polyethylene bag.

C. Shelf Life Analysis

The researcher conducted basic shelf-life analysis on the cookies through microbiological analysis, particularly focusing on the presence of molds over time. This method typically entails packaging the cookies in polyethylene bags and storing them at room temperature. Mold growth on cookies can be a significant indicator of spoilage and can affect the safety and quality of the product. By monitoring mold growth over a period, the researcher determined the shelf-life of the cookies and assessed their suitability for consumption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the discussion of the data based on the objectives of the study. This includes the level of acceptability of the panelists and the shelf life of cookies enriched with ground, candied, and dehydrated bamboo shoots.

Level of Acceptability of Cookies Enriched with Bamboo Shoots

A. Color

Table 3 presents frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of cookies enriched with different forms of bamboo shoots in terms of color. Each treatment represents a unique variation in the processing of bamboo shoots incorporated into the cookie recipes, namely ground bamboo shoots, candied bamboo shoots, and

dehydrated bamboo shoots. The data reveals varying levels of acceptability among participants for each treatment, indicating distinct preferences regarding the color of the cookies.

Table 3. Frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies in terms of color

Descriptive Equivalent	Treatment 327		Treatment 273		Treatment 732		Treatment 372	
	(Control)		(Ground)		(Candied)		(Dehydrated)	
	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop
Dislike extremely	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike very much	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike moderately	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike slightly	0	0.00	2	3.92	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neither like nor dislike	0	0.00	4	7.84	1	1.96	0	0.00
Like slightly	1	1.96	0	0.00	6	11.76	4	7.84
Like moderately	8	15.69	12	23.53	8	15.69	9	17.65
Like very much	22	43.14	17	33.33	13	25.49	16	31.37
Like extremely	20	39.22	16	31.37	23	45.10	22	43.14

Legend: Prop=Proportion

It was noted that for all treatments, there were no recorded instances of extreme dislike, suggesting a general level of acceptability. This indicates that incorporating bamboo shoots into cookies did not result in any overt aversion based on color alone.

Treatment 273, involving cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots, showed a relatively lower preference compared to other treatments, with only 31.37% of panelists expressing extreme liking. This finding could be attributed to the visual appearance of the cookies, which may have been altered by the presence of ground bamboo shoots. Previous research suggests that visual appearance significantly influences food acceptability and consumer preferences (Grunert, 2002). Cookies with visible particulates might evoke perceptions of non-conventional ingredients, potentially impacting consumer preferences.

In contrast, Treatment 732, which featured cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots, exhibited a more favorable response, with 45.10% of participants expressing extreme liking. The caramelization of bamboo shoots through the candying process may have contributed to the appealing color and flavor profile of the cookies. Research indicates that the addition of caramelized ingredients can enhance the sensory attributes and overall acceptability of food products (Peng et al., 2016).

Treatment 372, involving cookies enriched with dehydrated bamboo shoots, also demonstrated a high level of acceptability, with 43.14% of participants expressing extreme liking. The dehydrated form of bamboo shoots likely preserved their natural color

and texture, resulting in cookies that visually resembled traditional varieties. Studies have shown that the retention of natural colors in food products positively influences consumer perception and acceptance (Gibson, 2003).

Overall, the findings suggest that the method of processing bamboo shoots significantly impacts the acceptability of cookies in terms of color. While ground bamboo shoots may elicit a relatively lower preference due to their visual presence, candied and dehydrated bamboo shoots offer more visually appealing alternatives.

B. Aroma

As shown in Table 4, all treatments received positive responses in terms of aroma acceptability. Notably, the control sample garnered the highest percentage of respondents who liked the aroma extremely (49.02%), followed closely by Treatment 372 (dehydrated bamboo shoots) 43.14%, Treatment 732 (candied bamboo shoots) 41.18%, and treatment 273 (ground bamboo shoots) 35.29%.

This positive reception aligns with existing studies on the sensory properties of bamboo shoots. For instance, a study by Li et al. (2017) investigated the aroma profiles of different bamboo shoot varieties and found them to contain compounds contributing to desirable fragrances, such as 3-methylbutanal and 2,3-butanedione, which impart buttery and creamy notes. These compounds likely contribute to the favorable aroma perception observed in the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies.

Table 4. Frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies in terms of aroma

Descriptive Equivalent	Treatment 327		Treatment 273		Treatment 732		Treatment 372	
	(Control)		(Ground)		(Candied)		(Dehydrated)	
	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop
Dislike extremely	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike very much	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike moderately	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike slightly	0	0.00	2	3.92	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neither like nor dislike	0	0.00	4	7.84	2	3.92	0	0.00
Like slightly	3	5.88	0	0.00	7	13.73	5	9.80
Like moderately	6	11.76	12	23.53	8	15.69	13	25.49
Like very much	17	33.33	15	29.41	13	25.49	11	21.57
Like extremely	25	49.02	18	35.29	21	41.18	22	43.14

Legend: Prop=Proportion

C. Texture

As presented in Table 5, Treatment 273, involving cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots, showed a shift in preference towards the highest level of acceptability, with 41.18% of panelists rating the texture as "Like extremely". This suggests that the addition of ground bamboo shoots positively influenced the texture of the cookies, making them even preferable to a significant portion of participants compared to the control sample.

Table 5. Frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies in terms of texture

Descriptive Equivalent	Treatment 327		Treatment 273		Treatment 732		Treatment 372	
	(Control)		(Ground)		(Candied)		(Dehydrated)	
	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop
Dislike extremely	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike very much	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike moderately	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike slightly	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neither like nor dislike	1	1.96	3	5.88	2	3.92	1	1.96
Like slightly	3	5.88	1	1.96	7	13.73	5	9.80
Like moderately	16	31.37	10	19.61	8	15.69	9	17.65
Like very much	12	23.53	16	31.37	14	27.45	17	33.33
Like extremely	19	37.25	21	41.18	20	39.22	19	37.25

Legend: Prop=Proportion

Treatment 732, which involved cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots, also exhibited a favorable response from panelists regarding texture. 39.22% of panelists rated the texture of these samples as "Like extremely". Lastly, 37.25% of the panelists rated the texture of both the control sample and Treatment 372 as "Like extremely".

The ratings indicate a high level of acceptability for the texture of the sample cookies among the panelists. These findings align with previous research suggesting that the incorporation of unconventional ingredients, such as bamboo shoots, can positively impact the texture of food products. For example, a study by Wang et al. (2019) investigated the utilization of bamboo shoots in bakery products and found that the addition of bamboo shoots contributed to improved texture attributes, including tenderness and moisture retention.

D. Flavor

As shown in Table 6, as to the flavor, Treatment 732 involving cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots has the highest rating of acceptability as 58.82% of the panelists rated it as like extremely. This result aligns with studies on the impact of

sweetness on consumer preference. Research by Spence and Piqueras-Fiszman (2014) highlights that sweetness can enhance liking and acceptance of food products. The addition of candied bamboo shoots likely contributed to a pleasant sweetness, thus increasing acceptability in terms of flavor.

This is followed by Treatment 372 with a like extremely rating of 49.02%. In addition, 45.10% and 31.37% of the panelists extremely like the control sample and Treatment 273 respectively.

Table 6. Frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies in terms of flavor

Descriptive Equivalent	Treatment 327		Treatment 273		Treatment 732		Treatment 372	
	(Control)		(Ground)		(Candied)		(Dehydrated)	
	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop
Dislike extremely	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike very much	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike moderately	0	0.00	3	5.88	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike slightly	0	0.00	2	3.92	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neither like nor dislike	4	7.84	4	7.84	0	0.00	1	1.96
Like slightly	2	3.92	5	9.80	3	5.88	5	9.80
Like moderately	8	15.69	11	21.57	5	9.80	9	17.65
Like very much	14	27.45	10	19.61	13	25.49	11	21.57
Like extremely	23	45.10	16	31.37	30	58.82	25	49.02

Legend: Prop=Proportion

The absence of strong dislike responses across all treatments indicates that the addition of bamboo shoots did not negatively affect the acceptability of the cookies.

E. Overall Acceptability

As shown in Table 7, the most acceptable sample is Treatment 732, cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots where 47.06% of panelists extremely like it. The sweet and subtly flavored candied bamboo shoots likely contributed to the favorable reception, appealing to panelists' palates.

Table 7. Frequency distribution and proportions of the level of acceptability of the bamboo shoot-enriched cookies in terms of overall acceptability

Descriptive Equivalent	Treatment 327		Treatment 273		Treatment 732		Treatment 372	
	(Control)		(Ground)		(Candied)		(Dehydrated)	
	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop	f	Prop
Dislike extremely	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00

Dislike very much	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike moderately	0	0.00	3	5.88	0	0.00	0	0.00
Dislike slightly	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Neither like nor dislike	1	1.96	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Like slightly	2	3.92	3	5.88	5	9.80	1	1.96
Like moderately	9	17.65	12	23.53	9	17.65	12	23.53
Like very much	19	37.25	16	31.37	13	25.49	17	33.33
Like extremely	20	39.22	17	33.33	24	47.06	21	41.18

Legend: Prop=Proportion

Previous studies on the sensory properties of candied fruits can provide insights into the positive reception of Treatment 2. Research by Aguilar-Sanchez et al. (2019) found that candied fruits, with their concentrated sweetness and unique texture, were well-liked by consumers, indicating the potential for similar acceptability trends with candied bamboo shoots.

Shelf Life Analysis

Understanding the impact of bamboo shoots on the shelf life of cookies, particularly regarding mold formation, is crucial for ensuring food safety and quality. The cookies samples were sealed in polyethylene bags and stored at room temperature and observed for 7 days for the appearance of molds.

As shown in Table 8, molds appeared on the sixth day on the control sample where no bamboo shoots were added. This serves as the baseline for comparison. Treatment 273, which involved cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots, showed an accelerated onset of mold growth, appearing on the fifth day. Conversely, Treatment 732, utilizing candied bamboo shoots, exhibited a delayed onset, with molds appearing on the seventh day. Treatment 372, incorporating dehydrated bamboo shoots, displayed mold growth on the sixth day, consistent with the control group.

Table 8. Daily mold observation of cookie samples

Cookie Samples	Daily Observations						
	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7
Treatment 327 (Control Sample)	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	w/ molds	w/ molds
Treatment 273 (Enriched with Ground Bamboo Shoots)	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	w/ molds	w/ molds	w/ molds
Treatment 732 (Enriched with Candied Bamboo Shoots)	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	w/ molds

Treatment 372 (Enriched with Dehydrated Bamboo Shoots)	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	No molds	w/ molds	w/ molds
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These observations suggest that the form in which bamboo shoots are incorporated into the cookies influences their susceptibility to mold growth. Ground bamboo shoots, likely due to increased surface area and exposure to moisture, may provide a favorable environment for mold proliferation, thus shortening the shelf-life. On the other hand, candied bamboo shoots, which undergo a preservation process involving sugar, may exhibit mold inhibition properties, contributing to a prolonged shelf-life. Dehydrated bamboo shoots, while retaining some moisture, may have characteristics that do not significantly impact mold growth compared to the control.

Previous studies have highlighted the importance of moisture control in inhibiting mold growth in food products. Tapia et al. (2020) emphasized that high moisture levels provide an ideal environment for mold growth, leading to spoilage and potential health hazards. The presence of added fruits and vegetables introduces additional sources of moisture thereby accelerating the mold growth in the products.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were derived from the results of the study:

1. According to the findings, Treatment 732, cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots, were deemed the most acceptable in terms of color, flavor, and overall acceptability. In addition, the control sample was found to be the most acceptable in terms of aroma. Treatment 273, featuring cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots, emerged as the top choice for texture. A small percentage of 3.92% expressed slight dislike for the samples in terms of color, aroma, and flavor. Additionally, 5.88% moderately disliked the samples in terms of flavor and overall acceptability. Thus, cookies enhanced with bamboo shoots are regarded as highly acceptable.
2. Cookies enriched with ground bamboo shoots showed accelerated mold growth, with molds appearing on day 5, whereas those enriched with candied bamboo shoots displayed a delayed onset, suggesting potential mold inhibition properties, as molds appeared on day 7. Dehydrated bamboo shoot cookies exhibited mold growth like the control on day 6. Therefore, cookies enriched with candied bamboo shoots have the longest shelf life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Given the favorable acceptability of cookies enriched with bamboo shoots among the panelists, it is recommended that the developed cookies be sold in schools and

prepared for beneficiaries of school-based feeding programs. Additionally, conducting sensory evaluations with a wider audience could provide further insights into the acceptability of this product.

2. To potentially increase the shelf life of bamboo shoot-enriched cookies, other storing techniques and packaging materials, such as vacuum-sealed packaging or packaging with moisture-absorbing properties that provide a barrier against moisture and air, may be explored.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study, entitled *Assessment of Acceptability and Shelf Life of Cookies Enriched with Ground, Candied, and Dehydrated Bamboo Shoots*, adheres to the highest ethical standards throughout its execution.

Informed consent was obtained from all panelists involved. Panelists were provided with detailed information about the study objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, and they were given the opportunity to ask questions before providing their consent. Panelists were assured of their absolute freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any repercussions or consequences.

The privacy and confidentiality of all panelists were strictly maintained throughout the study. Any personal or sensitive information collected from participants was kept confidential and used only for research purposes.

Furthermore, this research was conducted in accordance with relevant guidelines and regulations governing research involving human subjects, as outlined by national and international regulatory bodies.

Overall, this study upholds the principles of integrity, respect for participants' rights, and responsible conduct of research, ensuring that ethical standards are rigorously upheld at all stages of the study.

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